

Second-order anisotropy due to magnetostriction for L1₀-FePt

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ABSTRACT

The effective magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy associated with magnetostriction is studied for tetragonal L1₀-FePt by means of first-principles calculations, which is expressed in terms of the intrinsic anisotropy for an undeformed crystal, the magnetostrictive coefficients, and the elastic tensor. A very small correction is found for the first anisotropy constant $\Delta K_1/K_1 = 0.07\%$, while a much more significant contribution is obtained for the second one $\Delta K_2/K_2 = 21.86\%$. General analysis of this effect for tetragonal crystals is provided, finding that ΔK_1 will be always positive for any stable phase with this symmetry. The potential implications and applications of these results are discussed.

1. Introduction

The magnetocrystalline anisotropy energy (MAE) plays a fundamental role in the design of modern magnetic materials in many technological applications since it allows to stabilize magnetization along some specific crystallographic directions [1]. Magnetoelasticity can also contribute to the overall anisotropy in addition to the intrinsic MAE (unstrained state). We can identify two types of magnetoelastic effects to anisotropy: (i) first-order anisotropy due to an external strain, and (ii) second-order anisotropy due to magnetostriction [2]. This second-order anisotropy naturally emerges from spontaneous magnetostriction due to magnetization process in an unconstrained sample (zero constant stress $\sigma = 0$). Namely, as the magnetization is rotated, the unit cell is distorted due to magnetostriction modifying the MAE surface. The measurement or calculation of MAE that includes second-order anisotropy due to magnetostriction is called MAE at constant stress E_K^σ , while intrinsic MAE of an unstrained unit cell (unchanged lattice parameters) is called MAE at constant strain E_K^ϵ [3], see Fig. 1. Typically, Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations of MAE are performed by fixing spins along different directions on an unstrained unit cell giving MAE at constant strain E_K^ϵ (intrinsic MAE). However, we point out that many experimental measurements of MAE are done on free samples, where magnetostriction takes place, and consequently corresponds to MAE at constant stress E_K^σ . Therefore, for a consistent comparison of MAE between experiment and theory, it is necessary to carefully check whether the second-order anisotropy due to magnetostriction should be included or whether it is negligible.

In the case of cubic crystals, the MAE at constant strain and stress read [2,4]

$$E_K^\epsilon = K_1(\alpha_x^2\alpha_y^2 + \alpha_y^2\alpha_z^2 + \alpha_z^2\alpha_x^2),$$

$$E_K^\sigma = (K_1 + \Delta K_1)(\alpha_x^2\alpha_y^2 + \alpha_y^2\alpha_z^2 + \alpha_z^2\alpha_x^2), \quad (1)$$

where α_i are the direction cosine of magnetization, K_1 is the intrinsic MAE first constant, and ΔK_1 is the second-order anisotropy due to magnetostriction giving by [2,4]

$$\Delta K_1 = \frac{9}{4}[(C_{11} - C_{12})\lambda_{100}^2 - 2C_{44}\lambda_{111}^2], \quad (2)$$

where C_{ij} are the elastic constants, and $\lambda_{100(111)}$ are the anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients. Here, we see that ΔK_1 could be positive or negative depending on the strength of factors $(C_{11} - C_{12})\lambda_{100}^2$ and $2C_{44}\lambda_{111}^2$. For instance, in cubic crystals where $|\lambda_{100}| \approx |\lambda_{111}|$ like in bcc Fe and fcc Ni, the second-order magnetostrictive contribution to magnetic anisotropy is typically small ($\Delta K_1/K_1 \sim 0.1 - 1\%$) [2,4]. However, note that at high temperatures close to T_C , ΔK_1 could be relevant also for the case of fcc Ni since it can change the sign of the effective K_1 [5]. Larger second-order magnetostrictive contribution to magnetic anisotropy is found in Rare Earth alloys, e.g. for TbFe₂ $\Delta K_1/K_1 \approx 20\%$ [6], where $|\lambda_{111}| \gg |\lambda_{100}|$.

The analysis of second-order magnetostrictive contribution to magnetic anisotropy in symmetries lower than cubic is more complex [3], and it is still rather quantitatively unexplored in many magnetic materials despite on its possible significant effect on MAE. For example, this is the case of L1₀-FePt, a tetragonal crystal that exhibits a very large easy axis MAE ~ 6.6 MJ/m³ [1] which plays a key role in magnetic recording

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Fig. 1. Schematic showing the difference between (a)–(b) MAE at constant strain E_K^ϵ , and (c)–(d) MAE at constant stress E_K^σ for L1₀-FePt. In MAE at constant strain, the lattice parameters of the unit cell are not allowed to relax (null strain $\epsilon = 0$) when magnetization is rotated from (a) ground state easy axis along c -axis \parallel [001], where there is no stress ($\sigma = 0$), to (b) hard plane along a -axis \parallel [100] leading to an internal stress ($\sigma \neq 0$). In MAE at constant stress, the lattice parameters are allowed to relax (null internal stress $\sigma = 0$) when magnetization is rotated from (c) easy axis to (d) hard plane, leading to a deformation of the unit cell due to magnetostriction ($\epsilon \neq 0$).

applications [7,8]. In our recent work [9], we theoretically studied the origin of the intrinsic MAE and magnetostriction for this material. Here, we extend this analysis to study the second-order anisotropy due to the magnetostriction.

The paper is organized as following; in next section we introduce main equations of the magnetoelastic theory for tetragonal crystals, and in Result and discussion section we use the *ab initio* obtained insights to determine the strength of the second order anisotropy due to the magnetostriction for L1₀-FePt. We finish with concluding remarks and general outlook in order to address the fact that the computational results should be performed as close to the conditions of the real experiments.

2. Methodology — theoretical

The study of MAE at constant stress for tetragonal crystals is more difficult than for cubic ones, so that it is convenient to briefly introduce the main theoretical equations for such analysis in this section. For the total energy density (E), energy per volume of a system, we include the elastic (E_{el}), magnetoelastic (E_{me}) and magnetocrystalline anisotropy at constant zero strain (E_K^ϵ) terms [10–12]

$$E(\epsilon, \alpha) = E_{el}(\epsilon) + E_{me}(\epsilon, \alpha) + E_K^\epsilon(\alpha), \quad (3)$$

where ϵ is the strain tensor and α is the normalized magnetization ($|\alpha| = 1$). Here, the elastic energy is considered up to second order in the strain, while the magnetoelastic energy contains only linear terms in the strain up to second order in the magnetization direction α . The MAE for the unstrained cell (at constant strain) includes the intrinsic first and second magnetocrystalline anisotropy constants K_1 and K_2 . For tetragonal single crystals with point groups 4 mm, 422, $\bar{4}2m$ and 4/mmm, these energy density terms read [10,12,13],

$$E_{el} = \frac{1}{2}C_{11}(\epsilon_{xx}^2 + \epsilon_{yy}^2) + C_{12}\epsilon_{xx}\epsilon_{yy} + C_{13}(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy})\epsilon_{zz} + \frac{1}{2}C_{33}\epsilon_{zz}^2 + 2C_{44}(\epsilon_{yz}^2 + \epsilon_{xz}^2) + 2C_{66}\epsilon_{xy}^2, \quad (4)$$

$$E_{me} = b_{11}(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) + b_{12}\epsilon_{zz} + b_{21}\left(\alpha_z^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right)(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy}) + b_{22}\left(\alpha_z^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right)\epsilon_{zz} + \frac{1}{2}b_3(\alpha_x^2 - \alpha_y^2)(\epsilon_{xx} - \epsilon_{yy}) + 2b'_3\alpha_x\alpha_y\epsilon_{xy} + 2b_4(\alpha_x\alpha_z\epsilon_{xz} + \alpha_y\alpha_z\epsilon_{yz}), \quad (5)$$

$$E_K^\epsilon = K_1(1 - \alpha_z^2) + K_2(1 - \alpha_z^2)^2, \quad (6)$$

where C_{ij} are the elastic constants, b_{11} and b_{12} are the isotropic magnetoelastic constants (b^{iso}), and b_{21} , b_{22} , b_3 , b'_3 and b_4 are the anisotropic magnetoelastic constants (b^{ani}) in Cullen et al. notation [10]. From the minimization of total energy Eq. (3) with respect to strain, one finds the following fractional change in length along a measuring length direction β [10,11]

$$\frac{l - l_0}{l_0} \Big|_{\beta}^{\alpha} = \lambda^{\alpha 1,0}(\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2) + \lambda^{\alpha 2,0}\beta_z^2 + \lambda^{\alpha 1,2}\left(\alpha_z^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right)(\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2) + \lambda^{\alpha 2,2}\left(\alpha_z^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right)\beta_z^2 + \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\gamma,2}(\alpha_x^2 - \alpha_y^2)(\beta_x^2 - \beta_y^2) + 2\lambda^{\delta,2}\alpha_x\alpha_y\beta_x\beta_y + 2\lambda^{\epsilon,2}(\alpha_x\alpha_z\beta_x\beta_z + \alpha_y\alpha_z\beta_y\beta_z), \quad (7)$$

where l is the length at the saturated state, l_0 is the length at reference demagnetized state with randomly oriented atomic moments (hypothetically paramagnetic state), $\lambda^{\alpha 1,0}$ and $\lambda^{\alpha 2,0}$ are the isotropic magnetostrictive coefficients (λ^{iso}), and $\lambda^{\alpha 1,2}$, $\lambda^{\alpha 2,2}$, $\lambda^{\gamma,2}$, $\lambda^{\delta,2}$ and $\lambda^{\epsilon,2}$ are the anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients (λ^{ani}). The magnetostrictive coefficients are related to the elastic and magnetoelastic constants through

$$\lambda^{\alpha 1,0} = \frac{-b_{11}C_{33} + b_{12}C_{13}}{C_{33}(C_{11} + C_{12}) - 2C_{13}^2}, \quad \lambda^{\alpha 2,0} = \frac{2b_{11}C_{13} - b_{12}(C_{11} + C_{12})}{C_{33}(C_{11} + C_{12}) - 2C_{13}^2}, \quad \lambda^{\alpha 1,2} = \frac{-b_{21}C_{33} + b_{22}C_{13}}{C_{33}(C_{11} + C_{12}) - 2C_{13}^2}, \quad \lambda^{\alpha 2,2} = \frac{2b_{21}C_{13} - b_{22}(C_{11} + C_{12})}{C_{33}(C_{11} + C_{12}) - 2C_{13}^2}, \quad \lambda^{\gamma,2} = \frac{-b_3}{C_{11} - C_{12}}, \quad \lambda^{\delta,2} = \frac{-b'_3}{2C_{66}}, \quad \lambda^{\epsilon,2} = \frac{-b_4}{2C_{44}}. \quad (8)$$

The reference demagnetized state with randomly oriented atomic moments (hypothetically paramagnetic state) is difficult to characterize both theoretically and experimentally. A more practical reference length (l'_0) corresponds to a demagnetized state with magnetic domains along all equivalent easy crystallographic directions (parallel and anti-parallel to the lattice vector c since L1₀-FePt is an easy axis magnet). For this reference demagnetized state, the fractional change in length reads [13]

$$\frac{l - l'_0}{l'_0} \Big|_{\beta}^{\alpha} = \lambda^{\alpha 1,2}(\alpha_z^2 - 1)(\beta_x^2 + \beta_y^2) + \lambda^{\alpha 2,2}(\alpha_z^2 - 1)\beta_z^2 + \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\gamma,2}(\alpha_x^2 - \alpha_y^2)(\beta_x^2 - \beta_y^2) + 2\lambda^{\delta,2}\alpha_x\alpha_y\beta_x\beta_y + 2\lambda^{\epsilon,2}(\alpha_x\alpha_z\beta_x\beta_z + \alpha_y\alpha_z\beta_y\beta_z). \quad (9)$$

In Mason notation the fractional change in length reads [3]

$$\frac{l - l'_0}{l'_0} \Big|_{\beta}^{\alpha} = \frac{1}{2}\lambda_1[(\alpha_x\beta_x - \alpha_y\beta_y)^2 - (\alpha_x\beta_y + \alpha_y\beta_x)^2] + (1 - \beta_z^2)(1 - \alpha_z^2) - 2\alpha_z\beta_z(\alpha_x\beta_x + \alpha_y\beta_y) + 4\lambda_2\alpha_z\beta_z(\alpha_x\beta_x + \alpha_y\beta_y) + 4\lambda_3\alpha_x\alpha_y\beta_x\beta_y + \lambda_4[\beta_z^2(1 - \alpha_z^2) - \alpha_z\beta_z(\alpha_x\beta_x + \alpha_y\beta_y)] + \frac{1}{2}\lambda_5[(\alpha_x\beta_y - \alpha_y\beta_x)^2 - (\alpha_x\beta_x + \alpha_y\beta_y)^2] + (1 - \beta_z^2)(1 - \alpha_z^2). \quad (10)$$

These magnetostrictive coefficients are related to those defined by Cullen [10] in Eq. (9) in the following way

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_1 &= -\lambda^{\alpha 1,2} + \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\gamma,2} \\ \lambda_2 &= \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\epsilon,2} - \frac{1}{4}\lambda^{\alpha 2,2} - \frac{1}{4}\lambda^{\alpha 1,2} + \frac{1}{8}\lambda^{\gamma,2} \\ \lambda_3 &= \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\delta,2} - \lambda^{\alpha 1,2} \\ \lambda_4 &= -\lambda^{\alpha 2,2} \\ \lambda_5 &= -\lambda^{\alpha 1,2} - \frac{1}{2}\lambda^{\gamma,2}.\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

The difference between MAE at constant stress (E_K^σ) and constant strain (E_K^ϵ) for tetragonal crystals was derived by Mason [3]

$$E_K^\sigma - E_K^\epsilon = \Delta K_1(1 - \alpha_2^2) + \Delta K_2(1 - \alpha_2^2)^2, \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta K_1 &= \frac{1}{2}C_{44}(4\lambda_2 - \lambda_1 - \lambda_4)^2, \\ \Delta K_2 &= C_{11}(\lambda_1^2 + \lambda_5^2) + C_{33}\lambda_4^2 + 2C_{12}\lambda_1\lambda_5 + 2C_{13}(\lambda_1 + \lambda_5)\lambda_4 \\ &\quad - C_{44}(4\lambda_2 - \lambda_1 - \lambda_4)^2.\end{aligned}\quad (13)$$

We see that the sign of ΔK_1 is the same as C_{44} , while the sign of ΔK_2 depends on the magnitude and sign of C_{ij} and λ_i . Since $C_{44} > 0$ is required to stabilize a tetragonal crystal [14], then we conclude that ΔK_1 is always positive for stable phase with this symmetry.

3. Results and discussion

By means of first-principles calculations (for details see Appendix and Ref. [9]) we present in Table 1 the elastic constants (C_{ij}), and anisotropic magneto-elastic and magnetostriction coefficients (b_i^{ani}) and (λ_i^{ani}) in Cullen [10] and Mason [3] notation, respectively. We can compare our theoretical elastic constants C_{ij} reflected in the bulk modulus with experiment that could be derived for the tetragonal crystals from the C_{ij} as $B = \frac{2}{9}(C_{11} + C_{12} + 2C_{13} + \frac{C_{33}}{2})$ [15]. The *ab initio* calculated values span the range of $B \approx 196 - 222$ GPa [16,17] as the experimental derived for $T \rightarrow 0K$ from polycrystalline is about $B = 233$ GPa [18]. Our calculated C_{ij} lead to the bulk modulus of 202 GPa which is within the range of other calculations, as well as slightly below the expected experimental value. The anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients show a span within the range of ($10^{-3} - 10^{-4}$) magnitude and one of them has even an opposite sign (λ_4).

We calculated intrinsic MAE constants K_1 and K_2 of the L1₀-FePt by fitting the total energy with different spin directions to the equation of MAE at constant strain E_K^ϵ for tetragonal crystal given by Eq. (6), see Ref. [9] for more details. The obtained results $K_1 = 15.16$ MJ/m³ and $K_2 = 0.32$ MJ/m³ are in good agreement with previous DFT calculations [19–21]. This result is also close to the experimental value $K_1 = 11$ MJ/m³ at $T = 4.2$ K reported by Hai et al. [22]. We note that the inclusion of the Hubbard U on 3d(Fe) and 5d(Pt) states could improve the correspondence between calculated MAE and its experimental value [20]. Next, using the values of magnetostrictive coefficients λ_i 's and elastic tensor C_{ij} , we determine ΔK_1 and ΔK_2 via Eq. (13), see the Table 2, where also values of iron based Rare Earths cubic Laves phases are displayed from Ref. [6]. The obtained value for $\Delta K_1 = 0.0102$ MJ/m³ is rather small in magnitude with respect to intrinsic K_1 , mainly due to the fact that λ_4 and λ_1 have different sign and therefore almost compensate the value of $4 \times \lambda_2$ as well as the elastic constant C_{44} has a moderate value, *i.e.* more than $3 \times$ smaller than C_{11} or C_{33} . For the more significant effect one would need a large difference between λ_2 and $\lambda_4 + \lambda_1$ and the latter two to have the same sign, unlike the situation here.

In contrast to ΔK_1 , the $\Delta K_2 = 0.0699$ MJ/m³ is larger in magnitude itself, and especially with respect to the intrinsic K_2 , see Table 2. In general, the largest contribution to ΔK_2 would arise from the fourth term in Eq. (13), however, several additional conditions would have to be fulfilled, at first *e.g.* all three λ_1 , λ_5 , and λ_4 will have to have

Table 1

Calculated values of elastic constants (C_{ij}), anisotropic magnetoelastic constants (b_i^{ani}), and anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients (λ_i^{ani}) in Cullen (C) et al. and W. P. Mason (M) notations [3,10] for the ordered L1₀-FePt phase at zero temperature.

C_{ij}	C_{ij} (GPa)	b_i^{ani} (C)	b_i^{ani} (MPa)	λ_i^{ani} (C)	λ_i^{ani} ($\times 10^{-6}$)	λ_i^{ani} (M)	λ_i^{ani} ($\times 10^{-6}$)
C_{11}	369.7	b_{21}	85.8	$\lambda^{\alpha 1,2}$	-378.6	λ_1	350.3
C_{12}	79.5	b_{22}	-46.1	$\lambda^{\alpha 2,2}$	542.1	λ_2	59.0
C_{13}	155.5	b_3	16.4	$\lambda^{\gamma,2}$	-56.6	λ_3	39.8
C_{33}	302.1	b_4	-47.7	$\lambda^{\epsilon,2}$	213.9	λ_4	-542.1
C_{44}	111.6	b'_3	70.5	$\lambda^{\delta,2}$	-677.5	λ_5	406.9
C_{66}	52.0						

Table 2

Calculated values (at $T = 0$ K) of anisotropy constants K_1 , K_2 , their second order corrections due to the magnetostriction ΔK_1 , ΔK_2 , and the ratios $\Delta K_1/K_1$, $\Delta K_2/K_2$ for L1₀-FePt. For comparison the experimental values [6] of cubic Laves phase iron-based Rare Earths alloys (at $T = 300$ K) are assessed.

Material	K_1 (MJ/m ³)	K_2 (MJ/m ³)	ΔK_1 (MJ/m ³)	ΔK_2 (MJ/m ³)	$\Delta K_1/K_1$ (%)	$\Delta K_2/K_2$ (%)
FePt	15.16	0.32	0.0102	0.0699	0.067	21.857
TbFe ₂	-6.30		-1.33		21.0	
DyFe ₂	2.45		-0.35		-14.0	
HoFe ₂	0.59		-0.008		-1.0	
ErFe ₂	-0.31		-0.02		6.0	
TmFe ₂	-0.04		-0.01		22.0	

the same sign (not case for FePt), or at second $\lambda_1 \ll 0$ or $\lambda_5 \ll 0$ and being highly anisotropic to each other $|\lambda_5| \neq |\lambda_1|$. For current situation where λ_4 is being negative, and both λ_5 and λ_1 are positive, the contribution from the fourth term of Eq. (13) results into negative one. However, the size of the first and second term (positive sign) is very large and positive. The 5th and 3rd terms basically cancels out as they have similar magnitudes and opposite signs, hence we ended up with overall positive ΔK_2 for FePt. Taken into account that $C_{11} \approx 2C_{13}$ the decisive coefficients are then λ_1 and $\lambda_5(\lambda_4)$ which indeed are of the orders of $\approx 10^{-3}$, and therefore the ΔK_2 is about 7 times larger than ΔK_1 , see Table 2.

4. Summary and conclusions

In this paper we have identified the second order anisotropy due to magnetostriction for K_1 and K_2 constants for L1₀-FePt alloy. The former one (K_1) is hardly affected as the ΔK_1 is basically governed by λ_1 and λ_4 , these magnetostriction coefficients, however, have opposite signs. Interestingly enough, the theoretical analysis of ΔK_1 reveals that it will be always positive for any stable tetragonal crystal ($\Delta K_1 \propto C_{44} > 0$), which facilitates the existence of an overall easy axis ($K_1 + \Delta K_1 > 0$).

The ΔK_2 of L1₀-FePt is found to be greater than ΔK_1 as well as the ratio $\Delta K_2/K_2$, affecting the anisotropy constant, *i.e.* increasing the effective K_2 by about 20%. However, since K_1 is much greater than K_2 , we conclude that the correction to MAE in unconstrained samples of L1₀-FePt arising from magnetostriction might be negligible at zero temperature. Although this correction can be neglected in this material, we point out that there are many other materials where these corrections could be comparable to intrinsic MAE, like in TbFe₂. In fact, it might also change the type of MAE as in fcc Ni at high temperature [5]. Note also that MAE at constant strain is typically computed in DFT calculations while MAE at constant stress is typically measured in experiment, so that in general one needs to account for ΔK in the theoretical calculations for a fair comparison with experiment. The extension of the presented analysis to finite temperature, as well as to other L1₀ phases could be interesting works for the future.

Theoretical analysis of ΔK_1 and ΔK_2 could be exploited in the design of magnetic materials for applications where MAE plays a key role. For example, this could be particularly useful in computational search for novel Rare-Earth free permanent magnets based on high-throughput screening techniques as an additional material parameter which could influence overall MAE [23].

CRedit authorship contribution statement

D. Legut: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **P. Nieves:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

Ab initio calculation

The total energy was calculated by non-collinear version (spin-orbit coupling included) of Vienna Ab Initio Simulation Package code (VASP) [24–26] employing projected augmented wave pseudopotentials [27] using generalized gradient approximation parametrized by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof [28]. The valence electronic configurations [Ar] $3p^6 3d^6 4s^2$ and [Xe] $5d^9 6s^1$ for Fe and Pt metals were used, respectively. The kinetic energy cut-off was set to 520 eV to ensure the total energy convergence of the order 10^{-9} eV/f.u. together with Fermi–Dirac smearing of 0.1 eV, and 36 963 k-points in half of the first Brillouin zone was sufficient for convergence of the calculated MAE parameters K_1 and K_2 [9]. The anisotropic magnetoelastic constants b^{ani} were calculated with the interface between MAELAS (-mode 2, energy-strain method) [29] and VASP using the settings described above. To compute C_{ij} we make use of the energy-strain method as implemented in AELAS [30] interfaced with VASP. The anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients λ^{ani} are obtained by inserting calculated b^{ani} and C_{ij} in Eq. (8).

Data availability

Data will be made in open access repository.

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